

Qualitative Roles of Performance Appraisal Function in Human Resources Management from Employee Focus

İnsan Kaynakları Yönetiminde Performans Değerlendirme Fonksiyonunun Çalışan Odağından Niteliksel Roller

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Abstract

Human resources management is the most important department in which the future situations of employees are dynamically planned, and task distribution and definitions are determined within the corporate relationship network. The task of career reconciliation between the organization and the employee, especially in changing sectoral dynamics. The human resources management unit is responsible for optimizing the internal and external dynamics of the organization. Human resources management performs this compliance optimization with its sub-functions. In particular, the correct determination and determination of the current situation and future positions of the employees is also an indicator of output within the organization. At this point, the performance evaluation function of human resources management has an important responsibility in fulfilling this task. As the world progresses in change, the needs and expectations of employees are also changing. At this point, the task is not only to measure the employee's performance but also to put forward the arguments that increase that performance. Organizations in which only the institution's needs are prioritized in the modern organizational structure fail in the long run in terms of competition. Therefore, individuals' involvement in determining the targeted performance indicators can make serious contributions to achieving the targeted outputs. In this regard, performance evaluation is the value put forward to provide information infrastructure to many departments such as career, reward and wage, talent management, training, and development. In this context, the aim of the study is; It is to reveal qualitatively what kind of structural and employee-focus performance evaluation has. In this direction, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 white-collar "employee-managers" working at the

corporate level in different sectors, content analysis was made with the NVivo qualitative analysis program, the data were analyzed, and the relationship densities were transferred. Research results; Employee-level information on performance evaluation has revealed the importance of arrangements.

Keywords: Human Resources Management, Performance Appraisal, Employee Performance.

JEL Codes: M1,M12,M19,M54

Özet

İnsan kaynakları departmanı, çalışanların kurumsal ilişki ağı içinde gelecek durumlarının dinamik olarak planlandığı, görev dağılımı ve tanımların belirlendiği en önemli departmandır. Özellikle değişen sektörel dinamiklerde örgüt-çalışan arası kariyer uyumlaştırma görevi İnsan kaynakları yönetimi birimi örgüt içi dinamikler ile örgüt dışı dinamikleri optimize etme sorumluluğu taşımaktadır. İnsan kaynakları yönetimi bu uyum optimizasyonunu alt fonksiyonları ile yapmaktadır. Özellikle çalışanların mevcut durumu ve gelecekteki pozisyonlarının doğru tespit ve tayini aynı zamanda örgüt içinde bir çıktı göstergesi olmaktadır. Bu noktada insan kaynakları yönetimi performans değerlendirme fonksiyonunun bu görevin yerine getirilmesinde önemli bir sorumluluk taşımaktadır. Dünya değişim içinde ilerlerken, çalışanların da ihtiyaçları beklentileri değişmektedir. Bu noktada görev salt çalışanın performans ölçümü değil aslında o performansı artırıcı argümanları da ortaya koymayı kapsamaktadır. Modern örgüt yapısı içinde sadece kurumun ihtiyaçlarının öncelendiği organizasyonlar, rekabet açısından uzun vadede başarısız olmaktadır. Dolayısı ile hedeflenen performans göstergelerini belirlemede işi yapan bireylerin de süreç içinde yer alması hedeflenen çıktılara ulaşmak için ciddi katkılar

sunabilir. Bu bakımdan performans değerlendirme; ortaya koyulan değerler, kariyer, ödül ve ücret, yetenek yönetimi, eğitim ve geliştirme gibi birçok departmana bilgi altyapısı sağlamaktadır. Bu bağlamda çalışmanın amacı; performans değerlendirmenin yapısal olarak, çalışan odağında nasıl bir karşılığının olduğunu niteliksel olarak ortaya koymaktır. Bu doğrultuda farklı sektörlerde kurumsal düzeyde çalışan 10 beyaz yakalı "çalışan-yönetici" ile yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler sağlanmış, NVivo nitel analiz programı ile içerik analizi yapılarak veriler analiz edilmiş, ilişki yoğunlukları aktarılmıştır. Araştırma sonuçları; performans değerlendirme ile ilgili çalışan düzeyli bilgilendirme düzenlemelerin önemini ortaya koymuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İnsan Kaynakları Yönetimi, Performans Değerlendirme, Çalışan Performansı.

JEL Kodları: M11,M12,M19,M54

Introduction

The human resources department is the most important department where the future status of employees within the corporate relationship network is dynamically planned and where the distribution of tasks and definitions is determined. The most important task of human resources managers is to achieve the optimum level of harmony between the organization and employees. Human resources management makes this harmony with its sub-functions. In particular, the correct determination and determination of the current status and future positions of employees is among the duties of the performance evaluation function. In this respect, the values revealed provide information infrastructure to many departments such as career, reward and wage, talent management, training, and development. Performance evaluation is a formal process for regularly reviewing and improving the organizational performance of employees (Homauni, 2018). Performance evaluation is an analysis of an employee's recent successes and failures, personal strengths and weaknesses, and suitability for promotion or further training (Mani, 2002). It is also a vital component of a broader set of human resource practices; it is the mechanism that assesses the extent to which each employee's daily performance is linked to the goals set by the organization (Coutts and Schneider, 2004). Defines performance evaluation as "a periodic or annual practice of evaluating and rating all employees of an organization on the results of performance based on job content, job requirements, and personal behavior in the position" (Alumni, 2015). In this respect, it is possible to evaluate performance evaluation as an impression of how to identify an employee's strengths and weaknesses and how to target how performance can be improved.

Evolutionary change represents an attempt to im-

prove aspects of the organization that lead to better performance and do not affect the fundamental nature of the work. In this respect, in terms of fundamental nature; performance evaluation is a key factor for developing an organization effectively and efficiently. Individual performance evaluation is very useful for the growth dynamics of the organization as a whole (Burke, 2008). Clifford (1999) in his research on the collective wisdom of the workforce said: "Today, faced with competitive pressures unimaginable to an earlier generation, managers need employees who think consistently and creatively about the needs of the organization, who are intrinsically motivated and have a deep sense of corporate stewardship. To achieve this, maximum attention must be paid to everyone's participation in corporate communication. Leaders and subordinates, questioners and answerers, all must begin to challenge themselves with a new level of self-awareness, candor, and responsibility. So, as managers, leaders, and boards of directors, we have to reveal how performance evaluation is perceived. This has two practical consequences, the first of which is that if employees are aware of the system by which they are measured and are satisfied and happy with it, the process can be closely monitored and continuity can be ensured through protection and improvement, and development efforts according to the period. The other consequence is that employees are not satisfied with the system. However, it seems that employees generally do not leave a job because of a poor performance evaluation tool. Rather, they leave because employers do not provide fair compensation and clear investment in career and advancement. Such departures can only be prevented through high-quality performance management (Verasai, 2021). Employee turnover resulting from such conditions can lead to the business cost of hiring and training new employees. A constantly changing workforce is a financial burden, and time is needed to recruit new people, during which time business tends to slow down. Despite the knowledge of all this, it will be seen that a scientific method based on efficiency does not work. Approximately 80 years ago, in Hawthorne's research, the foundations of human resource management were laid by revealing the effect of the manager's management style on the productivity of the employees and by recognizing the many factors that affect intrinsic motivation such as valuing people's participation. The second practical consequence is that an environment in which employees are not happy needs to be quickly designed and the system needs to be corrected from start to finish. These two practical results construct the purpose of this research. In this context, the study aims to qualitatively reveal how performance evaluation is structurally and employee-oriented. At this point, Mohrman (1989) reports that employees' participation in the process of per-

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formance evaluation positively affects their sense of justice, and their current performance, contributes to a clearer understanding of the future goals of the organization, and encourages employees to take more responsibility for development.

Institutional Framework for Performance Appraisal in Human Resource Management

Businesses have objectives such as profitability, growth, and sustainability. These objectives are realized with the resources available to the enterprise. Businesses want to control themselves in various ways in a competitive environment. This attitude is almost characteristic of companies that are aware of their corporate value and want to have a say on a national or international scale. Businesses use many evaluation methods. They want to determine their financial position by making ratio analyses. It makes a strategic positioning by investigating its strengths and weaknesses with Swot analysis. They want to keep their finger on the pulse of their customers through marketing research. The structure of an organization is determined externally by technology, environment, the situation of customers, the position of competitors, and internally by the talent potential of employees (Karaxha, 2019). It is noteworthy that while most of the variables affecting the structural situation are outside the direct control of businesses, employees are within the sphere of control. In this respect, for a business, employees represent dynamic skills that can directly touch and influence the organizational structure. Currently, employees play a key role in increasing dynamic skills and having a positive impact on overall business performance. At this point, the most important feature of employees is their ability to influence the performance of the organization (Zahra et al., 2006). At this point, focusing on increasing the competence of employees and improving their performance will significantly affect the performance of the organization. From this point of view, businesses that make various evaluations for all stakeholders and resources need to build a valid system of performance evaluation. This is because performance evaluation plays a vital role in any organization to develop its employees as well as to ensure that succession planning is done and that it achieves its goal of maximizing corporate profit and wealth (Alumni, 2015). It is a formal process by which employees' work activities are regularly reviewed and evaluated (Parsa et al., 2013) and stands as a prerequisite for other activities such as feedback, reward and punishment, staff development, and training in organizations (Stewart and Brown, 2019). Performance evaluation as a human resource management function has many benefits. These include an increase in employee motivation through the feedback process, information about working con-

ditions, and a wide range of other benefits such as encouraging strengths and improving weaknesses (Holt et al, 2007). In this respect, performance evaluation has the potential to increase employee motivation. Recognizing and rewarding employees' achievements creates an incentive for them to perform at a higher level. In particular, goal-setting and performance feedback processes can positively affect employees' commitment and motivation (Pechmann & Haase, 2021; Franco-Santos et al., 2020). Performance evaluations also provide an opportunity to learn about employees' expectations, fears, potentials, and goals. First, it links employee performance to the organizational mission. Second, it enables managers and employees to reflect on how the actions of other employees and external factors affect their performance. Third, it links the evaluation process to ongoing planning, budgeting, and decision-making. Therefore, a performance evaluation conducted within the framework of organizational goals can allocate effective use of resources, and goal revisions linked to processes of change (Levinson 1987). Performance evaluation is a fundamental part of the organization's evaluation system and the most important employee-based evaluation system. From a general framework, it is the only evaluation system in the business eco-system where resources are evaluated from various aspects and where emotions can be included in the evaluation with its intangible side. Since this study deals with the employees' approaches to the performance evaluation system, the study has been handled within the scope of the theory of sensory events. This theory provides insights into the performance evaluation process by addressing how work attitudes and behaviors emerge from emotions experienced in response to important work events (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996). Since the research is an effort to demonstrate quality, the context of the work environment, the quality and structure of the resources used in doing their jobs, and the relationships within the work environment are not independent of this process when employees evaluate the system by which they are measured, it is aimed to create a deep foundation by utilizing social cognitive theory and theoretical communication competence to strengthen the conceptual and theoretical aspect of the study. Among these theories, social cognitive theory forms the basis of situated cognition and dual processing research (Elsbach et al., 2005; Evans, 2008). Social cognitive theory can be read in terms of schemas. The schemas referred to here are cognitive phenomena that cannot be directly measured but are inferred from employees' self-reports (Fiske and Taylor, 1991). These phenomena provide information about the level of resources available to do a job and the quality of workplace communication. This stage is related to situated cognition. In the dual process, it is related to the reactive aspect that develops in the process that the employee reveals during the evaluation phase.

These approaches, which are capable of providing information and insights about the climate in the work environment, are related to the comfort of the employee in doing his/her job. For example, in a work environment with noise and heat problems, how productive can a person working with old applications and machines be and how satisfied can he/she be with the environment he/she is in? It would not be fair to hold the person responsible for his/her job performance here, and this would hurt the performance evaluation process (Verbos et al., 2013). At this point, the adequacy of the service provided, that is, the company's support for the employee's working environment, comes to the fore. Of course, the working environment is not the only variable that affects people's attitudes in the process. At this point, the people they work with are also important. The harmony between subordinate and superior relations and peer relations also has a serious role in the performance evaluation system in the eyes of the employee. In this respect, meetings and feedback sessions during performance evaluation processes provide a platform for brainstorming. Employees can develop new ideas to improve their performance and receive feedback from managers in this process. Such interactions encourage organizational innovation and allow employees to develop themselves (Camilleri, 2021). At this point, communication competence comes to the fore. This theory considers communication competence as a feature of the psychological climate of the organization. According to this theory, it emphasizes the harmony of the upward and downward flow of information within the organization (Senatra, 1980). The point of how performance evaluation is perceived can be good or bad. However, the goal for businesses is to get a good result. At this point, it is always preferred that employees' ideas are part of the solution. At this point, people's ideas are a component of the climate of the organization. This is, of course, important for an ecosystem that values what comes out of the employee's mouth and leads to improvement. Such a workplace encourages commitment through communication and can protect against alienation (Laabs, 1998). At this point, employees' participation in the performance evaluation process and the feedback they receive can have a significant impact on their job satisfaction and engagement. Moreover, employees' positive perceptions of the process may increase the perception of organizational support and motivation (Cuccurullo, et al., 2016). Much of the performance evaluation research has focused on the relationship between subordinates and superiors. Respectful interpersonal treatment is an important relational component of the evaluation process (Findley et al., 2000). It is a key element for ensuring transparency in the process and building trust among employees (Garengo, et al., 2021). A climate for positive coworker relationships is poten-

tially a powerful aspect of social cognitions about an organizational environment. Positive relationships with coworkers can generate positive social capital (Baker and Dutton, 2007). Bettenhausen and Fedor (1997) showed that relationship quality among coworkers influences positive reactions to peer and upward evaluation (Verbos et al., 2013).

In Masood et al, (2023), employees expressed concerns about performance evaluation in terms of reward system, incentives for improvements, health support, performance bonuses, employee capacity building, professional training, performance-based evaluations, scientific performance evaluation parameters, and social activities with colleagues. It follows that a well-structured performance evaluation process encourages employees to understand the evaluation criteria and participate in the process. Transparent communication also allows employees to voice their concerns about the process, which contributes to increased organizational trust (Garengo, et al., 2021).

Research Method

In this study, a qualitative research technique was used as the research method. Although there are many definitions of qualitative research, the most general definition is the holistic presentation of data collected through techniques such as observation, interview, and document analysis. In the study, the data obtained through the interview method were presented with the content analysis technique developed by Strauss and Corbin (1990). Thanks to this technique, the data were coded and categorized into themes. The main issue in content analysis is to select and categorize a small number of words that are critical for the subject from a large number of words in the answers given to open-ended questions (Miles & Huberman, 2015). NVivo 20 qualitative analysis software was used for the content analysis of the study research. Thanks to this analysis software, connections are made between the answers given by the participants, and the answers are made meaningful. All the data that emerged after the focus group interviews were coded in the first stage by reading the answers given by each participant in detail. In the second stage, the codes that create a meaningful whole among themselves are brought together and categories, i.e. themes, are determined. In the third stage, strategies for determining the validity and reliability of the research are created. In the fourth stage, the findings are defined and interpreted. The interview results were organized as texts and read one by one in detail for coding, and the meanings of each interview text such as words, sentences, or paragraphs were analyzed and coded. As a result of the coding process, the codes "Motivation", "Participation", "Brainstorm", "Career", "Support", "Feedback", "Commitment", "Satis-

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faction" and "Alienation" emerged. While preparing the question set for this research, Dobbins et al. (1990) Employee performance evaluation scale, Clifford's (1999) "The Collective Wisdom of The Workforce" and (Verbos et al., 2013) "Employee social cognition and performance evaluation process reactions" were utilized.

Findings

When we look at the person-based frequency of use of the codes obtained through the NVivo program, data that can be explained with the similarity of a heat density map were obtained. In this map, red colors are the codes that people never mention, yellow code is the most frequently mentioned code and green code density is the most frequently mentioned code. As a result of the Code-Based Frequency Analysis, it was understood that the codes were used with a total of 98 repetitions. The main purpose of document analysis is to emphasize the main theme variable that the related research focuses on. The most important feature of this finding is to reveal the key role in the study by utilizing the focus group experiences in which the interviews were conducted. We can also call this a phenomenon role. This finding conveys to us the intensity of common role emphasis among people who are independent of each other's thoughts. As a result of the Code-Based Frequency Analysis, it was seen that the motivation code was a phenomenon and each participant emphasized this code at least once. The phenomenon variable, which takes the leading role in the research, provides information about the conclusion reached by the relevant participants. Accordingly, performance evaluation for employees is characterized by motivation. The results of the document analysis are presented in Figure 1. Another finding obtained from the Nvivo program is the code relationship browser presented in Figure 2. This finding describes the relationship between the codes that stand out in the study.

	commitment	brainstorm	support	feedback	career	participation	satisfaction	motivation	alienation
1: Person 1	0	1	1	2	0	1	1	1	2
2: Person 10	1	1	0	1	0	2	2	3	1
3: Person 2	0	1	2	1	2	1	0	2	1
4: Person 3	1	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	1
5: Person 4	0	0	4	1	2	2	1	3	1
6: Person 5	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0
7: Person 6	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	1
8: Person 7	0	1	2	1	1	3	2	2	0
9: Person 8	1	0	1	2	0	2	2	1	1
10: Person 9	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	2	2

Figure 1. Code-Based Frequency Analysis

As a result of the analysis, the matrix in Figure 2 was obtained. The interaction between different codes was quantitatively transferred with the code rela-

tionship scanner. At this point, the aim is to interpret the relationship link between the codes qualitatively and quantitatively. The correlations revealed the elements that the managers included in the study used in their evaluations. The purpose of the evaluation is to show the strong and weak correlations between the codes. According to this matrix, the first findings show that the most important dyadic relationship is between "Motivation" and "Satisfaction". At this point, revealing what the drivers of satisfaction are will be instructive for the internal variables of motivation. At this point, participation, which is used 15 times, and brainstorming, which is used 6 times; it has been understood that people's participation in the performance evaluation process is not only a physical effect but also mental, the communication process of their direct voices and ideas should be emphasized. At this point, the feedback code used 12 times, which is another of the providers of satisfaction, provides a different perspective on the subject and adds strength. All this relationship network intensity emphasizes the intrinsic side of motivation, which has non-material providers. This can be explained by commitment, which is in the relationship intensity with satisfaction 5 times. On the other hand, the code of support, which is a tangible reward, is associated with the code of career, which is used 12 times, emphasizing the extrinsic aspect of the motivator. As a result of the research, at the opposite end, when the variable that evaluators would emphasize if there were no motivators was examined, the only direct relationship of this variable was found to be alienation from work and task.

	commitment	brainstorm	support	feedback	career	participation	satisfaction	motivation	alienation
commitment	5	0	0	1	0	1	5	3	0
brainstorm	0	6	0	0	0	3	0	1	0
support	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	3	0
feedback	1	0	0	12	0	1	2	0	0
career	0	0	4	0	12	0	0	4	0
participation	2	3	1	1	0	15	0	7	0
satisfaction	5	0	1	2	0	0	15	10	0
motivation	3	1	3	0	4	7	10	20	1
alienation	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10

Figure 2. Code Relationship Scanner

Another finding conveyed through the NVivo program is the word cloud analysis. Accordingly, the size, thickness, and color tones of the words in Figure 3 mean that they are used more frequently by the interviewed managers. In this context, the fact that the most frequently used concept with the concept of performance evaluation, which is the main subject of the study, is "motivation", as well as the frequency of use of concepts such as managers, sharing, goals and impacts, supports the fact that the interviewed group sees the meaning of performance evaluation for them as employees as a holistic inclusiveness for business goals.

Discussion

According to Tudor (2021), performance appraisal can increase employee motivation through the feedback process, provide an estimate of working conditions, and improve employee productivity by encouraging strengths and changing weaknesses. In addition, performance appraisal serves as an important transmission in the relationship between motivation and satisfaction. However, many organizations view performance appraisal as weak in meaning and inferior in importance (Homauni et al., 2018). However, as a critical function, performance appraisal has a wide range of effects from employee motivation to job satisfaction. Proper and fair management of these processes can increase employee loyalty to the organization and overall job satisfaction. Therefore, it is of great importance for organizations to design and implement performance systems meticulously. Homauni et al. (2018) reported that when managers are not involved in the performance appraisal process, feedback is excluded from the process, thus emphasizing the need for more involvement (Homauni et al., 2018). Indeed, Bloch et al. (2021) state that employee participation in performance appraisal processes strengthens employees' commitment to the organization and increases their job satisfaction (Bloch et al., 2021). Participation also allows employees to express themselves more and receive feedback that can contribute to their development. Idowu (2017) found that employees who provided information about performance appraisal targets were not well explained the process or even given feedback on performance, and attributed this to an inappropriate organizational climate or the questionable nature of the relationship between employees and managers. The study further emphasized the shortcomings of managers in designing performance appraisal indicators and pointed out that there is a capacity and competence problem for the role of managers in conducting appraisals. According to the study conducted by Longenecker (2017), the theme of how problems arise in employees who are away from the impact of performance appraisal was emphasized and it was pointed out that no matter how much organizational justice works, it cannot be checked whether the targeted results are achieved and as a result, even if an employee performs well, he/she cannot maintain or improve his/her performance because there is no feedback on this issue. At this point, it has been revealed that such negative experiences may cause employees to feel alienated from the organization, and unfair or inadequate feedback processes may make employees feel worthless, which may result in job dissatisfaction (Pechmann & Haase, 2021). On the other hand, a fair and transparent performance appraisal system increases employee loyalty and job satisfaction and reduces turnover (Franco-Santos et al., 2020). The most important premise here is feedback. Feed-

back, which is an important component of performance appraisal, helps employees understand their strengths and development areas. Effective feedback provides the necessary support for employees to improve themselves. When employees receive constructive criticism during the feedback process, it helps them improve their job performance (Dobija et al., 2019). Career planning sessions during performance appraisals, especially at the feedback point, allow employees to identify their long-term goals and take the necessary steps to achieve these goals. This process makes employees feel valuable and increases job satisfaction (Sheikh et al., 2022). Considering the results of the studies in the literature, the functionality of the performance appraisal process with the participation of employees affects many organizational outcomes such as increased or decreased motivation, commitment to the organization, job satisfaction, alienation level, feedback level, and effective communication. When evaluated from this point of view, the results of the research are consistent with the literature. The part where the research differs from other studies is that in many studies on performance appraisal, attention has been drawn to the problems and the hidden causes underlying these problems and the outcomes have been identified. At this point, literature focused on detection has been encountered. However, in this study, unlike other studies, suggestions for achieving a successful outcome in performance appraisal and impact roles are presented step by step.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Human resources management can fully fulfill its mission with the harmonious functioning of many functions. The good functioning of the performance evaluation system within these functions can make the human resources department stand out as a business function. The harmony optimization and settings of this department, which has many sub-functions, become effective thanks to the feedback of the performance evaluation system. At this point, the realization of efficiency is only possible by responding quickly to the feedback. In this respect, the performance evaluation system is expected to be contemporary, accepted by employees, and supportive of productivity and motivation. The latent information revealed by the employees in this study is in line with the literature and is in harmony with many models proposed in this field.

The results of the research offer recommendations to both academic studies and the real sector at certain points. These recommendations are also within the scope of the results of the study. The research aimed to qualitatively reveal how the performance evaluation system is perceived by the employees. Accordingly, to achieve the desired motivation as a result of targeting, the fact that employees are in

a socially oriented communication network such as working environment, collegueship, and subordinate-superior relations contributes to their satisfaction. However, when we look at the sub-variables that support satisfaction, more individual values come to the fore. At the beginning of these values, it is necessary to develop norms within the organization by asking employees to participate in the process, and asking them for their opinions about their work, if negativity occurs, it is necessary to develop norms within the organization by saying that “those who experience the solution of the problem best” can support the solution of the problem. At this point, participation is not only to participate in the process but also to take part in brainstorming practices while making new plans and taking action in the process. Of course, another variable that supports participation is feedback. All these variables invest in intrinsic motivation by making the employee feel valuable. Another result in the study is related to extrinsic motivation. At this point, employees who are supported especially in terms of economic conditions have more desire for career development and tend to invest in themselves. This means an intellectual capital contribution to the organization. Activating the variables underlying satisfaction also supports organizational commitment. This contribution is provided by the result of “alienation” obtained from the reverse question content. The practical model role of the study; supporting satisfaction for motivation, and preparing an environment suitable for participation for the construction of this satisfaction, as a result, it supports commitment at one end and shifts towards alienation at the other end.

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